

The ERMIS Nanosatellite Constellation: Defence and Security Applications

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Abstract

The ERMIS mission, part of Greece's £200M National Small Satellite Programme, is a pioneering constellation of three cubesats (two 6U and one 8U) designed to enhance national security and defence capabilities. Coordinated by the National Kapodistrian University of Athens with key partners, ERMIS will deliver advanced connectivity and Earth observation services tailored to Greece's needs. Scheduled for launch in January 2026, the £4.8M project features a 5G-IoT network, inter-satellite links, and hyperspectral imaging (5m GSD) for applications such as precise agriculture monitoring and real-time data collection. Funded by the EU's NextGenerationEU and the Greek Ministry of Digital Governance, ERMIS bolsters Greece's space infrastructure and can support security and defence through secure laser optical downlinks (1 Gbps), paving the way for a robust national space presence.

Keywords

ERMIS mission, small satellite constellation, space security, defence applications, hyperspectral imaging, 5G-IoT connectivity, Greece space programme

1. Introduction

The advent of microelectronics, materials, sensors, microprocessors, artificial intelligence, new manufacturing techniques such as 3D printing, coupled with private initiatives and investment has allowed for the miniaturisation of satellites and for the more frequent and affordable launch of them to orbit. This has allowed small satellites (mass < 500 kg) to become an important tool for many nations, businesses, start ups and has led to a massive expansion of space applications through constellations and mega-constellations of small satellites in remote sensing/earth observation, satellite communications, technology demonstration and space exploration. Small satellites have become the 'Personal Computer – PC – of space' allowing various actors including start ups, academia, scientists and industry to develop and demonstrate an idea, concept or business application in orbit in a very short time ¹.

ERMIS is a pathfinder demonstration of key space connectivity capabilities linked to, Greece's 200M€ national small satellite project using a constellation of small satellites. Coordinated by the National Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA) the consortium includes leading space, small satellite and IoT/communications entities OQ Hellas, University of Patras, University of the Aegean and the National Observatory of Athens.

As the first Greek small satellite constellation, ERMIS will bring novel space communications (Low Earth Orbit 5G-IoT communication services, Inter-Satellite Link (ISL) and laser optical downlink), hyperspectral earth observation applications focused on national needs (e.g. precise agriculture) and small satellite technology capabilities for Greece and Europe, and create new unprecedented space capacities, synergies, and infrastructure in Greece.

The ERMIS mission consists of a constellation of three (3) advanced (two 6U and one 8U) cubesats focused on demonstrating key communications/connectivity and earth observation technologies and applications, utilizing a mixture of existing Greek space technology such as communications (IoT/5G, ISL), CCSDS on-board data processing, state-of-the-art FPGA accelerators for hyperspectral image compression and optical channel-coding, attitude control tracking algorithms, laser optical communications demonstrating 1 Gbps downlink to the Helmos Optical Ground Station, hyperspectral imaging (5m GSD), associated EO applications and national space infrastructure for its ground segment. Launch of the ERMIS constellation is planned for the end of 2025 ².

The initiative underpins efforts – led by the European Space Agency (ESA) on behalf of the Greek Ministry of Digital Governance – to expand the nascent space industry in Greece, enabling the digital transformation of society while creating jobs and generating prosperity, as part of the nation’s EU-funded Recovery and Resilience Facility. The ERMIS 4.8M€ project is funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU and by the Greek Ministry of Digital Governance and is coordinated by the Department of Aerospace Science and Technology of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (www.aerospace.uoa.gr) ³.

2. Nanosatellites

In recent years, small satellites have opened up new possibilities for the space industry. Ranging from the size of a refrigerator to a shoebox, these very small spacecraft are much smaller than traditional ones. This allows small satellites to leverage benefits like lower development and launch costs, rapid deployment, and operation in large constellations. Countless missions, including navigation, research, and remote sensing, rely on these compact devices. The miniaturisation of spacecraft has brought in numerous attractive scientific and business possibilities, and the space sector is exploiting the benefits of this more sustainable and democratic approach.

When discussing spacecraft, the term “small” is typically used to describe their mass and size. Any satellite with a mass below 500 kg is considered a small satellite, also called a smallsat, or a miniature satellite. Satellites small in size are not new, though modern ones differ from their predecessors in many ways, the most notable of which is the use of widely accessible microelectronics in conjunction with innovative management approaches. This allows for the creation of spacecraft, working alone or in satellite constellations that can carry out complex functions with great utility while consuming far less space, money, and time than previous generations ¹.

Compared to the market for large-size spacecraft, the financial and technological barriers to entry into the smallsat market are typically much lower. Because of their tiny size, easier construction, and greater launch possibilities, these devices are affordable to many businesses and organizations.

From their initial beginnings as experimental entities, smallsats have come a long way to become an independent type of satellites and market segment, that is now indispensable to space

operations. Recent developments in miniaturization, in-space propulsion, onboard processing and control, and communication systems have completely transformed the space sector by allowing smallsats to carry out complex tasks that were previously achievable only with larger spacecraft⁴. There is no universally accepted categorization for small-size satellites, and various factors are considered when classifying these spacecraft. These factors include mass, size, orbit, application, mission duration, and more. Table 4 shows the most prevalent classification of small satellites which is based on mass and size.

Types of small satellites based on mass and size			
Type	Mass (kg)	Max. dimensions (m)	Orbit
Minisatellite	100–500	3–10 /	GEO, MEO, LEO, HEO
Microsatellite	10–100	1–5	LEO, HEO
Nanosatellite	1–10	0.1–1	LEO, HEO
Picosatellite	0.1–1	0.05–0.1	LEO, HEO
Femtosatellite	<0.1	0.01–0.1	LEO, HEO

Table 1: Small Satellite Classification [1, 4]

Figure 1: Nanosatellites (< 10 kg) Launch to Date (from nanosats.eu)

Figure 1 shows the significant adaptation and proliferation of small satellites and in particular nanosatellites (< 10 kg) to date.

3. The National Small Satellite Program

Since 2017, the General Secretariat of Telecommunications and Post of the Ministry of Digital Governance (MDG) is the responsible authority for all civilian space matters in Greece. The MDG collaborates with the Ministry of National Defence in the field of space systems and applications of MoD competence, focusing on enhancing national security and defence capabilities. The Secretariat is tasked to develop and implement the national space policy, strategy and plan. It represents Greece in all European and international organisations including European Union Space Programme Agency (EUSPA), European Space Agency (ESA), International Telecommunications Union (ITU) as well as in other European or International Organizations with focus in Space related activities ⁵.

Law 4727/2020 - Digital Governance (Incorporation into Greek Law of Directives (EU) 2016/2102 and (EU) 2019/1024) and Other Provisions), defines Greece's objectives for participation in the European Space Agency. Specifically, Article 119, Paragraph 9, states that these objectives are pivoting around four objectives¹:

1. ***Strengthen national security and Defence, especially with the utilization and development of space infrastructure.*** Ensure national autonomy in safety and security (e.g. border control, disaster management) by enhancing existing infrastructures (e.g. GreekCom) and developing new ones (e.g. small satellites). The goal is to autonomously respond to national safety and security needs.
2. ***Development of the Greek space industry.*** Maximise the integration of Greek companies into the European industrial space landscape. The goal is to create a sustainably competitive Greek space industry.
3. ***Utilise of space data and the development of relevant applications.*** Foster the integration of space into the society and economy, by facilitating the use of space technologies and applications to support public policies and business development (e.g. telecom, transport, maritime, agriculture, energy, and environment). The goal is to create public and commercial services.
4. ***Support space research and innovation.***

The related activities and projects are:

1. ***Development of a national small sat programme.*** Achieving autonomous capabilities to respond to national needs, strengthening the Greek industry competitiveness with the possibility for commercial utilisation in the global market.
2. ***Flight heritage.*** Achieving flight heritage through the EU, ESA and national programmes by maximising technological and financial synergies.
3. ***Ground infrastructure.*** Utilising and further developing existing infrastructures: nationally or privately owned stations (e.g. Tanagra, Koropi, Ag. Paraskeui), telescopes, lasers, radars, etc

¹ Greek National Law, 2020 N4727.

4. **User alignment (ministries).** Supporting through space the development implementation and monitoring of sectorial policies (e.g. telecom, transport, maritime, agriculture, energy, environment, safety and security)
5. **Exploit data of existing infrastructure.** Opening of public information will increase the size of the domestic market, especially when the private and the public sector work together. In navigation Galileo will boost commercial activities and integrated applications will tie Earth Observation and navigation to telecommunications.

The National Small Satellite programme is a 200M€ multi-mode space programme funded by the European Commission Recovery and Resilience Facility focused on developing new space capabilities, capacities, technologies and applications for Greece ⁵. It is composed by multiple elements such as:

- Upgrade of existing telescopes/infrastructure to Optical Ground Stations (OGS)
- A cubesat based in-orbit Verification/Validation and Demonstration (IOV/IOD) programme with the launch of 11 cubesats in 2025 and 2026
- Development of a national small satellite Assembly, Integration and Testing (AIT) facility
- Development of a radar facility for Space Situational Awareness (SSA) applications linked to the EU SST initiative
- Development of a 130M€ earth observation capability which includes the launch of 7 optical (Open Cosmos), 2 SAR (ICEYE), 4 Thermal IR (Ororatech) micro and nanosatellites in 2026, together with the development of a space data government hub and a group of specialised earth observation R&D projects for niche applications such as precision agriculture, forestry, security and water

Figure 2: ESA/Greek Cubesat in Orbit Validation Project Logo [3]

4. The ERMIS Hellenic Cubesat Demonstration Mission

ERMIS is a pathfinder demonstration of key space connectivity and earth observation capabilities linked to, Greece’s 200M€ national small satellite project using a constellation of small satellites. Coordinated by the National Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA) the consortium includes leading space, small satellite and IoT/communications entities OQ Hellas, University of Patras, University of the Aegean and the National Observatory of Athens. As the first Greek small satellite constellation, ERMIS will bring novel space communications (Low Earth Orbit 5G-IoT communication services, Inter-Satellite Link (ISL) and laser optical downlink), hyperspectral earth observation applications focused on national needs (e.g. precise agriculture) and small satellite technology capabilities for Greece and Europe, and create new unprecedented space capacities, synergies, and infrastructure in Greece.

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Figure 3: ERMIS Mission Partners and Mission Patch

The ERMIS Nanosatellite Mission objectives are:

- Demonstrate an optical laser communication payload achieving up to 1 Gbps downlink capacity to the OGS compatible to SDA Optical Communications Terminal Standard and optionally to upcoming CCSDS O3K standard.
- Acquire hyperspectral image cube focused on precision agriculture using a hyperspectral imager with 8 days average revisit time.
- Incorporate state-of-the-art high-data rate FPGA accelerators to optimize the execution of CCSDS algorithms for onboard payload data compression of both Hyperspectral and panchromatic images.
- Conduct in-orbit demonstration and validation of Attitude Determination and Control System (ADCS) control algorithms and their suitability for use with the Optical Link.
- Spearhead the development of new space connectivity capacities in Greece, including a Payload Clean Room and a small satellite ground station.
- The mission shall demonstrate the capability to operate an IoT communications payload from orbit
- The mission shall demonstrate the capability to provide IoT connectivity using a Nanosatellite platform by connecting to a (at least 1) terrestrial terminal
- The mission shall demonstrate the capability to exchange information between its platforms via an Inter Satellite Link
- Develop new space capabilities, applications and infrastructure in Greece

Figure 4: ERMIS Mission Architecture

Figure 4 shows the ERMIS mission architecture block diagram including all elements of the space and ground segment. The mission objectives are a combination of earth observation and connectivity goals. To address all objectives, two different platforms will be used: (i) two 6U cubesats equipped with communication payloads operating in S-Band and with an intersatellite link (ii) an 8U cubesat equipped with a high-resolution hyperspectral payload and an Optical Communications Terminal. The two platforms will share the majority of the bus, mission analysis and operations planning. Accommodating the different payloads inevitably leads to some differences in bus component selection. Table 1 shows the ERMIS orbit (500 km SSO) and launch date which will take place in January 2026 (Transporter 16) and uses a Falcon 9 rideshare opportunity.

Altitude	500 km +/- 8 km
Inclination	~97.5 +/- 0.01 deg (Sun Synchronous)
Local Time of the Ascending Node	11am/11pm
Eccentricity	0.001
Baselined Launch Provider	Exolaunch (rideshare programme)
Date	Q1 2026

Table 2: ERMIS Orbit and Launch Details

Figure 5: ERMIS 1 and 2 Nanosatellite CAD Drawings with S-band Payload based on a 6U Cubesat (OQ Tech)

Figure 6: ERMIS 3 Nanosatellite CAD Drawings with 5-m GSD Hyperspectral and Laser Optical Link Payloads based on a 8U Cubesat (University of Athens and Patras)

Figure 7: Computer Visualisation of the ERMIS Constellation with all 3 nanosatellites over Greece

Currently all satellite components, ground stations are being assembled in the University of Athens (UoA) clean room. ERMIS 1-3 will be tested over the summer of 2025 at the UoA AIT/clean room facilities. Delivery of the satellites to the launch broker is expected to take place in November 2025, in preparation for a launch in January 2026 on a SpaceX Falcon 9.

5. Defence and Security Applications

The ERMIS nanosatellite constellation will focus on demonstrating key telecommunications and earth observation capabilities which can have significant defence implications. The ERMIS 1 and 2 nanosatellites will be able to offer low memory messaging services based on OQ Hellas' S-band network and constellation as a global satellite 5G IoT operator providing uninterrupted cellular coverage for assets and machines anywhere on the planet⁶. OQ uses a fleet of nanosatellites in LEO which connect to its proprietary ultra miniature dual-mode satellite-cellular IoT modem and tracker which is a plug and play small, low-cost, and low-power solution that can collect data from more than 1000 sensors. The modem/tracker has built-in GPS, and supports 5G NB-IoT, GSM, LTE-M, and bi-directional Satellite links with data bundles ranging from few Kbytes to Megabytes per day.

Using an existing fleet of 10 nanosatellites which is being rapidly scaled up, low data services are offered for various civil and defence related applications such as:

- Hybrid Satellite-Cellular Terminal: Uses a flexible, robust, and programmable dual-mode terminal with pre-paid data packages. It is ideal for remotely monitoring and controlling fixed and mobile assets in industries as diverse as transportation, oil and gas, utilities, maritime, agriculture, and more. It supports GSM/LTE-M/NB-IoT and Satellite link both in uplink and downlink. It can connect to 1000 sensors using multiple I/Os. It supports multiple SIMs and can be powered with a battery that survives multiple years. All this is for a fraction of the cost used by incumbent operators.
- Smart Mobility: Connected smart vehicles/drones are entering the market and offer companies the chance to deliver goods further and in more efficient ways. Tracking of fleets and goods is not possible outside cities where no cellular coverage is available. OQ offers an end-to-end satellite 5G integrated solution that allows monitor assets and fleets in real time, anywhere they may go. Furthermore, bi-directional communication to machines can be offered such as banking ATMs in poor connectivity areas. A dual satellite-terrestrial solution that can switch automatically between OQ and partner networks can create robust communications for mobile platforms.
- Smart Ocean: Maritime connectivity today is limited to expensive satellite VSAT and M2M high-end terminals, this is not suitable for IoT data collection and control. IoT/satellite solutions can help track fishing boats, smart nets, weather buoys, and commercial containers. In addition to that real-time tracking solutions can be provided for transport ships and yachts. Finally managing sensors and devices on offshore rigs,

underwater pipes and oil wells have never been easier, all using a highly secure and reliable system.

- **Smart Energy:** IoT/satellite solutions can enable efficient operations of smart energy grids efficiently, and at full capacity and avoid disruption or loss of assets by giving full access remotely to manage your applications. This includes SCADA systems, pipeline monitoring, and leak detection, predictive maintenance reports of machinery and windmills, inventory and asset tracking, mining, environmental monitoring, oilfields monitoring, tracking of workers and their well-being, and finally industrial smart metering.

Figure 8: OQ Technology Model and Smart Mobility, Smart Ocean Applications

ERMIS-3 is a pilot earth observation nanosatellite with a SIMERA Sense 5m GSD hyperspectral payload, a laser optical link which can provide secure downloads of satellite data and a Greek Payload and Data Processing Unit (PDP) which can compress, distribute satellite data on board the satellite platform. The mission application for ERMIS-3 is focused on precision agriculture and specifically:

- **Vegetation mapping:** Hyperspectral imagery (HyI) can support the mapping of plant varieties.
- **Crop health monitoring:** HyI can detect stress in crops, nutrient deficiencies, and disease outbreaks, enabling timely interventions.
- **Soil analysis:** HyI can assess soil composition, moisture content, and fertility levels.
- **Precision agriculture:** Data from hyperspectral imagery helps optimize irrigation, fertilization, and pest control.

Hyperspectral imaging at 5 GSD can give very unique features for earth observation for a multitude of applications. Figure 9 shows the preliminary analysis of imaging Greece with a single satellite which can provide full coverage of Greece's territories and islands twice a month.

Figure 9: Coverage Analysis of Greece with the ERMIS-3 Nanosatellite

In the interest of imaging the whole Greek region, a coverage analysis was conducted to deduce the maximum imaging time required to capture a complete pass over Greece, as shown in Figure x. For a duration of 7 days with 7 passes one will have a minimum duration of 107s, maximum duration of 130 s with a minimum revisit time of 13 hours and a maximum revisit time of 60 hours.

Table 3: ERMIS-3 Passes and Contact Time Analysis at 500 km SSO

ERMIS-3 even as a single satellite will enable unique mapping capabilities which can support various defence and security applications for Greece and enable scaling up ERMIS with multiple additional satellites to provide a high revisit earth observation capability in the near future. Further to the ERMIS-3 imaging capabilities, ERMIS-3 carries a unique, high performance laser optical link provided by Astrolight and which will be linked with multiple Optical Ground Stations (OGS) including the Helmos OGS upgraded through ESA’s Scylight programme and operated by the National Observatory of Athens (NOA).

6. Conclusion

ERMIS is a groundbreaking project which promises to push cubesat technology boundaries. Three satellites are currently being developed and assembled in Greece two 6U (10 x 20 x 30 cm) and one 8U (10 x 20 x 40 cm) for satellite communications and earth observation applications. Combined with other satellite investments currently taking place in the Greek National Small Satellite Programme, Greece will be launching 24 small satellites in the next 16 months creating a comprehensive constellation with R&D, operational, communications and earth observation capabilities which can support a multitude of national needs including defence and security. ERMIS is a cubesat constellation ‘made in Greece’ which is creating very unique national capabilities and links with academia and industry and can become the backbone of a new space generation in Greece.

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Short Biography:

Professor Vaios Lappas holds a BEng in Aerospace Engineering from Ryerson University (Canada), an MSc in Space Technology from NASA Goddard via the International Space University (France), and a PhD in Space Vehicle Control from the University of Surrey (UK), and has led significant research grants on satellite technology, space missions, and space debris, funded by the US Air Force, NASA, Airbus, ESA, and the European Commission, including the EU-funded QB50 and RemoveDEBRIS missions, the EDA EuroSWARM defence project, and the ERMIS nanosatellite constellation (Greek Ministry of Digital Governance/ESA); he currently serves as Professor of Aerospace Systems and Head of the Department of Aerospace Science & Technology at the University of Athens (Greece) and Consulting Professor at Cranfield University (UK), focusing research on unmanned vehicles for defence, satellite systems, launch vehicles, and small satellites (EU, US Air Force, ESA), while teaching Flight Controls, Dynamics, and Satellite Communications and supervising MSc and PhD students in Astronautics, Space, and Autonomous Systems at Cranfield.

Dr. Antonios Paschalis, born in 1960, is Professor at the Department of Computer Science and Telecommunications at the University of Athens, where he directs the Digital Systems and Computer Architecture Laboratory (DSCAL) and the Interdisciplinary MSc in Space Technologies, Applications and Services (STAR), serves as an academic member of the si-Cluster Board, and has held roles including member of the Hellenic Space Agency Board, the provisional assembly for the Department of Aerospace Science and Technology (UOA), and President of the Department of Computer Science and Telecommunications (UCA, 1916-1920); he earned a B.Sc. in Physical Sciences (1982), an M.Sc. in Electronic Automation, and a Ph.D. in High Reliability Computing (1987) with a fellowship from the National Research Centre “Demokritos,” all from NKUA’s Department of Physics, bringing over 10 years of experience in designing on-board payload data processing units for space applications and recognition as a Golden Core Member of the IEEE Computer Society.